

The moral values and characteristics of the main character in *Skyscraper* by Rawson Marshall

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Abstract : This research aims to show the moral values and characteristics of the main character in Rawson Marshall Thurber's *Skyscraper* movie. The study employed the descriptive qualitative methodology. The data analysis method utilized a new criticism analysis, which includes analyzing the structure of the theme, the structure of feelings, the structure of tone and atmosphere, and the structure of the mandate. The research object under study covers the entire duration of the movie. The researchers concluded that: 1) The packaging of moral values in *Skyscraper* movie by Rawson Marshall Thurber has three moral values that help build the character of the main character. 2) The main character in this movie is portrayed as persistent, honest, and courageous. 3) The observations indicate that the main character's characteristics are influenced by moral values, highlighting the significance of moral principles in overcoming challenges and emphasizing that a positive mindset leads to optimism, perseverance, and a good attitude.

Keywords : *literature, moral values, main character, movie analysis*

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INTRODUCTION

Literary works must possess beauty, genuineness, and creative value in both their content and expression. Noor in Putri et al (2021) stated that literary works are creative works of art such as novels, poetry, short stories, dramas, etc. Literary works encompass not only novels, poems, and dramas, but also movies. The movie is one of the artistic phenomena that emerges most magnificently. The popularity of movies as a subject in literary studies has increased due to the widespread adaptation of literary works into movies, including novels and short tales. A movie can enhance the enjoyment of a literary work more vividly since it is in the form of audio-visual to convey a story.

According to Hornby (2006) in Kaka & Gde Nova (2023), a movie is a collection of moving pictures captured with sound that tells a story and is shown at the cinema or other devices. It is a type of literature, namely an art form and communication media whose influence can reach all social communities (Sulayani et al., 2021). Because of its power and capacity to reach a wide range of social groups, a movie has the potential to impact audiences. In this context, movies and society are understood linearly. However, the reality that appears in the movie is not real so it can be real-life imitations. Mukarromah (2019) said that as an audiovisual medium, the movie can be used in the process of building emotions, attitudes, and even problem-solving. In addition, movies serve as an educational medium that portrays human life, making it easier for audiences to embrace learning. They also provide educational resources that may convey various lessons, including moral values. Moral values are defined as guidelines that assist a person in deciding to be able to distinguish between right and wrong (Kaka & Gde Nova, 2023). This indicates that movies have a significant impact on society because of the message they convey. The criticism that appears against this perspective is based on the argument that movies are portraits of the society in which movies are made.

Movies contain moral values commonly found in reality that refer to society's life (Humaira, 2018). Sulayani et al (2021) stated that morals are similar to mandates, serving as positive messages communicated through character, conduct, and behavior. Hornby (2010) in Sulayani et al (2021) proposed some kinds of moral values such as; bravery, humbleness, honesty, justice, steadfastness, respectability, sympathy, cooperativeness, thankfulness, trustworthiness, sincerity, and others Moral values are crucial for our lives since they are linked to conventions, manners, and behavior. They are highly needed by our students whose morale starts to degrade. (Bastian et al., 2021). In fact, every day, moral degradation is evident in our surroundings. It occurs due to students' inability to apply positive principles instilled in them at school or home. Therefore, they must be supervised by parents and get a moral education from school to develop and uphold excellent ethics.

Moral values can be portrayed in a movie through the characters. According to Nawawi (2022), characters are people who are shown in a narrative work or drama or movie which readers interpret as having moral qualities and certain tendencies as expressed in speech and what is done in action. A character is a person who plays a figure in a fictional story or drama (Nurgiyantoro, 2013). Characters are frequently referenced in reflections on life. One could have the role of a good character, and the other could have the role of a bad (Rahmah et al., 2021). It can be inferred that characters are individuals who portray roles in stories and can act authentically to create narratives that seem genuine.

One of the movies that shows the strong character is the *Skyscraper* movie. This movie depicts a character who works as a security supervisor at the tallest and safest fictional Skyscraper movie in the world, The Pearl. This figure represents a character with a strong character, steadfast in his stance, and committed to truth even in challenging circumstances.

The representation of a character can serve as a model for developing character traits in individuals. Therefore, this research attempts to highlight the moral values and qualities that define the main character in Rawson Marshall Thurber's *Skyscraper* movie. It is expected to provide a deeper comprehension of how one's moral fortitude can impact or manifest in the process of acquiring character education.

METHOD

This research used the descriptive qualitative method, which focuses attention on the general principles that underlie the expression of meaning in social phenomena. Qualitative research gathers data in the form of words or visuals rather than numbers. Taylor et al (2015) proposed that qualitative research encompasses all forms of inquiry that generate descriptive data—individuals' written or spoken words, as well as observable behavior. Moleong (2013) in Rahmah et al (2021) added that qualitative is research that uses a natural setting to interpret the phenomena which occurred and carried out by involving various existing methods. In this study, data was collected through observation while watching a movie. In addition, researchers use the document research method to analyze the script of the *Skyscraper* movies. The analysis focuses on events and texts presented as visual displays that convey values and highlight the character of the primary protagonist, Will Sawyer. The researchers selected Will Sawyer using the purposive sampling method. According to Mulyana (2000) in Anggriawan (2022), purposive sampling is one of several types of non-probability sampling that is usually used in qualitative research. It is considered nonprobability since researchers do not intend to generalize their research findings. Purposive sampling involves the researcher selecting specific samples without using random approaches, solely based on the researcher's subjective assessment.

In this study, researchers used new criticism analysis, intrinsic analysis, and extrinsic analysis. According to Van Luxemburg et al (1988) in Martono (2010), this genre emerged as a reaction to previous literary criticism which focused too much on aspects of life and psychology of the author and literary history. Hawkes in Martono (2010) also proposed that a work of fiction consisting of several elements that build it up using language as a tool, thus forming a meaningful story. Full comprehension of meaning can only be achieved by correctly combining its components. This analysis model is divided into four major structures, which include: (1) theme structure, (2) feel/feeling structure, (3) tone and atmosphere structure, and (4) mandate structure (Bunga et al., 2021). The researchers made the decision to use the movie *Skyscraper* as analysis material based on the preceding description. New criticism analysis techniques, such as intrinsic and extrinsic analysis, will be applied during the investigation. Researchers were drawn to the movie because it was packed with moral values that had such deep significance that they belonged in a motion picture. The main character, Will Sawyer, portrayed during the catastrophe that befell him, is another topic of interest to researchers.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Some touching lessons we might take from the movie *Skyscraper*: family safety is the top priority. The term "Friends in Struggle" signifies that Will and one of his buddies, who both survived a previous rescue mission, have a positive relationship up to 10 years more. This movie teaches us that placing trust or confidence in someone else can be challenging. The significance of collaboration and mutual protection is exemplified by the situation of Will's wife and twin children who were stuck on the 98th level of the building, emphasizing the value of teamwork and safeguarding one another. Perseverance is exemplified by Will Ford, showing that with strong determination and drive, one can overcome even the most challenging obstacles. We must persevere and have faith that things will improve if we approach them with

seriousness and sincerity. These five moral lessons are ubiquitous throughout people's lives. Therefore, researchers analyze the moral message of the movie utilizing new criticism analysis, intrinsic analysis, and extrinsic analysis.

The moral value and character of the main character in the movie *Skyscraper* can be effectively analyzed by utilizing the four structures (theme, feeling, tone and atmosphere, and mandate structure) as part of the approach of new criticism. The moral values and character of the main character in the *Skyscraper* movie can be observed clearly, with the following analysis:

a. Theme Structure

The theme structure involves organizing the primary concepts or subject matter presented by the writer in literary works. The story scheme comprises various units, including the story title, setting, and plot. This system serves as the author's guide for organizing ideas in a story.

1) Story Title

Based on prior research findings. This research focuses on a film called *Skyscraper*. Researchers infer that the word *Skyscraper* refers to a tall building based on the title. A skyscraper is a noun that refers to an extremely tall building. Skyscrapers taller than 300 meters are referred to as supertall. Buildings of lesser stature may be labeled as skyscrapers if they overshadow the nearby environment. The term "skyscraper" was coined in the late 19th century to describe large skyscrapers, reflecting the awe inspired by the construction of towering structures in New York City. Hong Kong now holds the top spot globally for having the highest number of skyscrapers compared to other cities. Hong Kong currently has over 7,500 buildings.

2) Story Setting

The location in the film represents the time, place, and atmosphere of the events in the plot. This occurs because the characters in a story exist within a specific setting and time. The events in the story happen at a certain time and location. The location and time of an occurrence are referred to as the setting. The location in a story can be based on real events or the author's imagination.

a) Time Setting

It is a certain time or period in which the actions of the story take place. This movie is structured around three dominant timelines that interconnect and enhance one another. Firstly, the background of life Will is a former FBI member who lost a lower leg on a rescue mission where he had to rely on prosthetic limbs. Then, the second setting moves to the time when Will, who now works as a security consultant, brings his wife and two children to a luxury apartment in a *Skyscraper* movie in Hong Kong. Finally, an outline of the time frame that describes the moment Sawyer believes that the building was attacked by terrorists who made him unable to stay.

b) Place Setting

It is another physical location/building where the events in the story occur. In this 169-minute movie, the researchers looked at the setting that dominates the movie *Skyscraper* movie is the tallest and safest *Skyscraper* movie in Hong Kong called *The Pearl*. The building was designed with super-sophisticated technology with a more than 1,000 meters height. It has 240 floors consisting of a magnificent indoor garden, fancy restaurants, malls, exclusive residences, penthouses, a helipad, and office space at the top level with 25,000 ultra-HD screens.

c) Atmosphere Settings

It is an intrinsic element connected to the psychological state that emerges automatically with the plot. An engaging story is characterized by the specific mood in which it unfolds, such as joy, emotion, grief, or tension. The story's atmosphere is typically established by the portrayal of the main character. Will Sawyer, the protagonist of the movie, encounters three prominent locales that play a crucial role in the storyline.

3) Story Plot

Plots are events that are presented in a story based on cause and effect. An event is a series or scene or scene that builds the course of the story. There are three models of events, namely functional events, related events, and reference events. In this section, the researcher will only explain functional events and related events. Researchers have identified a minimum of 20 functional events in this movie. Based on researchers' observations, there are at least three main conflicts that affect the storyline or plot of this movie. The three conflicts are divided into two kinds: internal conflict when Sawyer's bosses convinced him that the skyscraper would be impenetrable. Another internal conflict is the action of Will Sawyer when saving his family from the fire of the building he occupies. The external conflict happened when Will, trusted as security head for a skyscraper, was framed and considered the mastermind of a terrorist attack.

The climax involves Sawyer, framed as the mastermind of a building attack, becoming a fugitive and attempting to save his family trapped in a building fire and clear his name from slander by identifying the mastermind behind the incident.

Figure 1

The movie's theme structure suggests a forward plot, with the main actor facing a slanderous tragedy. However, the author presents the plot in a tight order, making it easy to understand the series of stories presented. This tight forward plot allows for a clear understanding of the storyline.

4) Feel/feeling Structure

The movie's feel/feeling structure reflects the author's views on the objects in his work. The story revolves around a father who loves his family, proves his unyielding nature through trials, and is full of responsibility for his work. The main character is committed to honesty and demonstrates his love for his family through his unwavering dedication to his work. Researchers analyze moral values using this structure, focusing on the main character's intelligence, courage, honesty, perseverance, responsibility, and love for his family.

5) Tone and Atmosphere

Tone and atmosphere are crucial aspects of literary work. Tone influences the reader's attitude and can influence their actions, such as advising, ridiculing, or being straightforward.

Atmosphere, on the other hand, is the state of the reader after reading a work. Both are closely related, with sad tone causing compassion, and criticism causing rebellious moods. For example, in *Skyscraper*, absurd scenes can tense the audience, as seen with Will Sawyer jumping through a tall building.

Figure 2

The author also aims to communicate the importance of a child's confidence in their parents, as illustrated by a child overcoming fear by believing in their parents' guidance.

Figure 3

The movie also portrays a gloomy atmosphere when the protagonist's son is abducted by terrorists, leaving the father feeling powerless as a pistol is held on his son's head. The audience also hoped to be swept away by the emotional setting of the scene.

Figure 4

6) Mandate Structure

The author's aim is for the audience to desire that objective after watching his work. Furthermore, it is a message that the writer aims to communicate to the audience using language. The message can also be inferred from the author's word arrangement. The *Skyscraper* movie depicts a father's unwavering determination to protect his family from a building fire. Furthermore, maintain a strong dedication to the promise made evident when the protagonist secures employment.

The study analyzes the moral values and character of the main character, Will Shawyer, to understand the relationship between issues and their resolution. The main character's honest attitude towards his job and unyielding attitude towards saving his family from fire are interpreted as moral values, demonstrating that honesty leads to truth and happiness. Will Shawyer, framed by his friend, struggles to escape the police chase and climb to the top of a building to save his family.

The moral value of the main character, Will Shawyer, is based on his unwavering determination to achieve his goals. He saved his family from fire and terrorists, and even climbed the tallest building without assistance, despite his limping leg. This bravery is exemplified by his actions in saving his family and climbing the tallest building, a feat impossible in real life. The moral value of this character is that despite the challenges, we must persevere, as God will reward those who dare on the path of truth.

CONCLUSION

The analysis of *Skyscraper* by Rawson Marshall Thurber reveals three moral values that shape the character of Will Shawyer. Shawyer maintains honesty despite being encouraged by his companion to commit a crime. The second point is to persist and show a relentless spirit without giving up. The main character demonstrates bravery by breaking into a high-rise building on their own, emphasizing the third moral value in the plot. The movie highlights the significance of honesty, steadfastness, and bravery when confronting life's challenges, as divine assistance is always available to those who are ready to confront them. In addition, the movie also depicts a character who perseveres in addressing challenges and displaying a good attitude. The author emphasizes the importance of moral principles in overcoming life's obstacles, asserting that a positive mindset results in optimism, perseverance, and a positive attitude. The story implies that God will offer help when needed, and that honesty and truthfulness can prevail even in difficult circumstances.

The *Skyscraper* film has been analyzed for several aspects, including the contributions of the screenwriter and director, society, and academics. The author recommends enhancing the story to make it more memorable and profound to effectively communicate the intended message. The movie appeals to those who enjoy action scenes and portrays a positive message of bravery and integrity in protecting one's family. The film can be used as a teaching medium for academics, especially in language learning, by enhancing contextual and visual comprehension. This method can facilitate academics' comprehension of language, even if they do not fully understand it. The *Skyscraper* movie deserves careful consideration and evaluation.

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